

group of the acid and formation of 1 : 1 hydroxo complex in accordance with the equations 3 and 4.

The breaks at $m=2$ and $m=6$ in the 2 : 1 mixture of ligand and metal (curve 3') further confirms the above formation.

The present investigation clearly reveals the formation of 1 : 1 hydroxo complex above pH 7.0.

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Studies on 6-Heteropoly Vanadomolybdate

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A few heteropoly vanadates have been reported^{1,2} but with the exception of 12-vanadophosphate anion, none of them has been well characterised^{3,4}. The present short communication deals with the preparation, characterisation and X-ray crystal diffraction studies of a new 1 : 6 heteropoly complex of vanadium with molybdenum as the heteroatom.

Water solutions of molybdic acid and potassium metavanadate were taken in the molar ratio of 1 : 12 and refluxed for nearly 4 hr. The solution was left in atmosphere for a few hours and then crystallised under vacuum when small needle shaped red crystals came out which were recrystallised thrice from hot water. The complete analysis of the compound was done by chemical and colorimetric analysis, from which the percentage of potassium, vanadium and molybdenum were found to be 10.62, 27.88, 8.70 against the theoretical calculated values 10.70, 27.99, 8.78. The percentage of water together with oxygen was calculated by difference which came to 37.434. From these percentage composition data the ratio between Mo : V came to 1 : 6, which agreed with the formula $K_8 [MoV_6O_{19}] 11H_2O$. The representation of the formula was according to the views of Keggin⁵.

X-ray Crystallographic data and determination of molecular weight : A single crystal of the compound was mounted along its longer dimension : a axis. The oscillation photographs did not show mx, my and mm

symmetry. Zero level, first level and second level Weissenberg photographs were taken. The absence of Weissenberg photographs of OKO for $K \neq 2n$ and hol for $K \neq 2n$ identified the space group as P_{21}/C . The angle was determined by the method of 'level offsets'. The final values of cell dimensions are : $a = 9.42 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 15.38 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 10.12 \text{ \AA}$ and $\beta = 105^\circ$, hence the system is monoclinic. The volume 'V' per unit cell was calculated to be $1416.18 \text{ \AA}^3$. The number of molecules per unit cell 'Z' was fixed to be 2. The observed density measured by flotation method $\rho_{obs} = 2.53 \text{ gml}^{-1}$. From the relation $\rho_{obs} = \frac{1.66MZ}{V}$, the molecular weight 'M' of the compound came to 1081 against the theoretical value 1092.95, calculated from its stoichiometric formula. This definitely shows that the compound is monomeric.

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Determination of Oxidizing Powers of Tinperoxychromate and its Water Decomposition Product

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RIESENFIELD and Coworkers¹ have shown the existence of two classes of peroxychromate, blue and red, derived respectively from $HCrO_5$ and H_3CrO_5 . Raynold and Reedy², Klemm and Werth³, Beltron Martinez and Rea⁴ have prepared the perchromate of calcium, potassium and magnesium respectively.

Schwarz and Giese⁵, Prakash and Rai⁶ on the basis of their studies formulated chromium peroxychromate as CrO_4 and $Cr_2(Cr_2O_{10})_8$ respectively.

The present paper consists of the study of tinperoxychromate and its water decomposition product. It throws light on the constitution of tinperoxychromate and thus explains the formation of decomposition product.